

शोध - प्राज्ञिका

रजत जयन्ती वर्ष

उत्तर प्रदेश राजकीय महाविद्यालय एकेडमिक सोसाइटी

Uttar Pradesh Govt. Degree Colleges' Academic Society

पंचदश अधिवेशन एवं राष्ट्रीय सेमिनार

27 - 28 मार्च, 2011

उत्तर प्रदेश उच्च शिक्षा विभाग द्वारा प्रायोजित

दृष्टि: 2020

VISION: 2020

आयोजक

महाराजा बिजली पासी राजकीय स्नातकोत्तर महाविद्यालय

आशियाना, लखनऊ

सेमिनार आयोजक

संरक्षक

डॉ. रामानंद प्रसाद

निदेशक

उच्च शिक्षा उत्तर प्रदेश

संयोजक

डॉ. राम सहाय

प्राचार्य

महाराजा बिजली पासी राजकीय स्नातकोत्तर महाविद्यालय
आशियाना, लखनऊ

आयोजन सचिव

डॉ. यू.के. सिंह, एसोशिएट प्रोफेसर

महाराजा बिजली पासी राजकीय स्नातकोत्तर महाविद्यालय
आशियाना, लखनऊ

डॉ. सी.एस. वर्मा, एसोशिएट प्रोफेसर

महाराजा बिजली पासी राजकीय स्नातकोत्तर महाविद्यालय
आशियाना, लखनऊ

सलाहकार मण्डल

डॉ. एस.ए. अली

क्षेत्रीय उच्च शिक्षा अधिकारी, लखनऊ

डॉ. रणविजय सिंह

प्राचार्य, राजकीय महाविद्यालय, औराई, संत रविदास नगर

कोषाध्यक्ष

डॉ. सरला सिंह, एसोशिएट प्रोफेसर

महाराजा बिजली पासी राजकीय स्नातकोत्तर महाविद्यालय
आशियाना, लखनऊ

सदस्य

1. डॉ. प्रेमलता राय

2. श्री एच.आर नांगलिया

3. कु. कल्पना सिंह

4. श्रीमती दीप्ति सोनकर

5. डॉ. रीना गुप्ता

6. श्री अजीत कुमार

7. डॉ. गुन्जन शाही

8. कु. शालिनी कनौजिया

9. डॉ. के.के. विश्वकर्मा

एकेडमिक सोसाइटी शोध-पत्रिका
Academic Society Research Journal

Volume- XV, No. I, March- 2011

(Bilingual Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences)

Editor:

Dr. Ram Sahai

Editorial Board:

Dr. Prem Lata Rai

Dr. H.R. Nangalia

Dr. U.K. Singh

Dr. C.S. Verma

Dr. K.K. Vishwakarma

Annual Official Publication of :

Uttar Pradesh Govt. Degree Colleges' Academic Society, Allahabad.

एकेडमिक सोसाइटी शोध-पत्रिका

Academic Society Research Journal

Volume- XV, No. I, March- 2011

(Bilingual Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences)

© editor

Price : Not Priced

Disclaimer : The views expressed by the authors in their respective articles published in *Academic Society Research Journal*, are their own. The Editor and the Editorial Advisory Board are in no way responsible any liability arising out of the contents of these articles.

Publisher : Maharaja Bijli Pasi Govt. P.G. College, Aashiana, Lucknow

All disputes subject to the jurisdiction of courts in Lucknow.

अनुक्रमणिका

क्रम सं. विषय	लेखक	पृ.सं.
1. सदेश	3-9
2. संयोजक की कलम से...	11
3. ई-एजुकेशन : एक परिचय	डॉ. चन्द्र विजय चतुर्वेदी	15
4. Seminar Proceeding	Dr. C.S. Verma, Dr. U.K. Singh	22
5. Girish Karnard and His Various Performative Techniques: An Overview	Dr. K.K. Vishwakarma, Dr. U.K. Singh	26
6. Higher Education in India: Challenges and Opportunities in XII th Five Year Plan	Dr C.S.Verma	30
7. Nutritional Study on Soybean (Glycine max L.) Enriched Wheat Flour Chapati	Shalini Kanojia	33
8. Ground Water Studies in the Stressed Urban Area of Lucknow City	Dr. H.R. Nangalia, Mr. Abhishek Kumar Singh	35
9. Problems of Higher Education in India....	Vijay Laxmi Yadav	39
10. Architecture: Formation of the Traditional	Dr. Rashmi Srivastava	41
11. Minerals and Ayurvedic System of Medicine	Dr. Satyendra Singh, Dr. Navneeta Singh	45
12. Environmental Changes and Global Warming..	Dr. Mahendra Prakash	48
13. A Study of Capital Structure Determinants.....	S.K. Agarwal	51
14. Vision 2020 : Right to Sight of India	Dr. Atul Kumar Kanojia	57
15. Energy Plantations – A Hope to Climate Crisis	Dr. Alok K. Srivastava	59
16. Globalization and Indian Women	Dr. R.R.Bakshi	61
17. A Comparative Study of Reaction Time.....	Dr. Sheel Dhar Dubey	64
18. Bioremediation : An Approach	Dr. Manjari Nautiyal	67
19. Environment and Agricultural Development	Dr. N.K. Srivastava	69
20. Privatization of Education : A Boon	Dr. Seema Singh	74
21. Application of Information	Meenakshi Lohani, Punit Tripathi	76
22. Humanism in Miss Lillian Hellman's	Pankaj Singh	79
23. Plants Associated With Domestic Rituals	Poonam Agarwal	86
24. A Critical Evaluation of Role of Govt.	Dr. Ramesh Chandra Verma	91
25. Social Inequality: A Blot on Political	Dr. Suman Gupta	93
26. Role of Home science for upliftment	Dr. Nitu Singh	96
27. Mysticism in the works of Tagore and Kabir : ..	Dr. Deen Dayal	98

Application of Information and Communication Technology in Higher Education: Vision 2020

* Meenakshi Lohani
** Punit Tripathi

The new learning opportunities across the globe have transcended the conventional "book-teacher" model with the growing inclusion of information and communication technologies. The nature of learning and teaching has undergone a sea-change owing to increasing interaction with more accessible global telecommunication networks supported by the content of the Internet. New options for distance education are opening up newer avenues and driving the shift from traditional learning communities towards unrestricted lifelong learning possibilities. The shift from teacher-centered to learner-centered learning means teachers at all levels need to embrace new information and communication technologies and education and training need to keep up with the advances of new technologies. As new technology is being accepted as the catalyst for new learning environments, access to communication has become crucial. Access to communication and information is indeed a fundamental human right. The challenges to access to information and communication are tremendous in developing countries like India and it is in this context that information and communication technologies are becoming more and more vital.

A substantive progress in implementation of information and communications as well as quality of life and development cannot be achieved without preparing people for a knowledge society. This, to a certain extent, involves creating an environment amenable for diffusing computers to schools, training the population in computer application and building a solid national computer and communication science education. The challenge here is not to put computers on the desks but also to create the conditions for bright students to emerge with solutions to actual problems, perhaps this could lead to a national industry comparable to current agricultural production. The two main aims are:

Student-centred learning:

Technology has the capacity to promote and encourage the change of education from a very teacher directed enterprise to more student-centred. This includes:

- The proliferation of capability, competency and outcomes focused curricula
- Moves towards problem-based learning
- Increased use of the Web as an information source. Internet users are able to choose the experts from whom they will learn.

The use of ICT in educational settings, by itself acts as a catalyst for change in this domain. ICTs by their very nature are tools that encourage and support independent learning. Students using ICTs for learning purposes become immersed in the process of learning and as more and more students use computers as information sources and cognitive tools, the influence of the technology on supporting how students learn will continue to increase.

* Assistant Prof., Dept. of Geography, Km Myawati Govt. Girls P.G. College, Badalpur, G.B. Nagar.

** Technical Lead, McKinsey & Company, Gurgaon.

Supporting knowledge construction:

The emergence of ICTs as learning technologies has coincided with a growing awareness and recognition of alternative theories for learning. In the past, the conventional process of teaching has revolved around teachers planning and leading students through a series of instructional sequences to achieve a desired learning outcome. Contemporary learning theory is based on the notion that learning is an active process of constructing knowledge rather than acquiring knowledge and that instruction is the process by which this knowledge construction is supported rather than a process of knowledge transmission. Learning approaches using contemporary ICTs provide many opportunities for constructivist learning through their provision and support for resource-based, student centered settings and by enabling learning to be related to context and to practice. Use of ICT in learning settings can act to support various aspects of knowledge construction and as more and more students employ ICTs in their learning processes, the more pronounced the impact of this will become.

Current Issues of Information Technology applications in Indian Higher Education system:

A number of issues have emerged from the uptake of technology whose impacts have yet to be fully explored. These include changes to the makeup of the teacher pool, changes to the profile of who are the learners in our courses and paramount in all of this, changes in the costing and economics of course delivery.

In the past, the role of teacher in an educational institution was a role given to only highly qualified people. With technology-facilitated learning, there are now opportunities to extend the teaching pool beyond this specialist set to include many more people. The changing role of the teacher has seen increased opportunities for others to participate in the process including workplace trainers, mentors, specialists from the workplace and others. Through the affordances and capabilities of technology, today we have a much expanded pool of teachers with varying roles able to provide support for learners in a variety of flexible settings. This trend seems set to continue and to grow with new ICT developments and applications. And within this changed pool of teachers will come changed responsibilities and skill sets for future teaching involving high levels of ICT and the need for more facilitative than didactic teaching roles

Earlier, education has been a privilege and an opportunity that often was unavailable to many students whose situation did not fit the mainstream. Through the flexibilities provided by technology, many students who previously were unable to participate in educational activities are now finding opportunities to do so. The pool of students is changing and will continue to change as more and more people who have a need for education and training are able to take advantage of the increased opportunities. Interesting opportunities are now being observed among school students studying university courses to overcome limitations in their school programs and workers undertaking courses from their desktops. Compared to traditional forms of off-campus learning, technology-facilitated learning has proven to be quite expensive in all areas of consideration, infrastructure, course development and

course delivery. We may have to brace ourselves for the advantages and affordances which will improve the quality of education in the near future to also increase components of the cost.

The present study has sought to explore the role of ICT in education in the changing patterns of imparting higher education. The continued use and development of ICTs within education will have a strong impact on:

- What is learned;
- How it is learned;
- When and where learning takes place;
- Who is learning and who is teaching.

The upshot of all this activity is that we should see marked improvements in many areas of educational endeavour. Learning should become more relevant to stakeholders' needs, learning outcomes should become more deliberate and targeted, and learning opportunities should diversify in what is learned and who is learning. At the same time, quality of programs as measured by fitness for purpose should continue to grow as stakeholder groups find the offerings matched to their needs and expectations.

Once again ICTs serve to provide the means for much of this activity to realize the potential it holds. The focus will be on a combination of traditional and more flexible courses, enriched by modern technologies. Each higher education institution will be encouraged to open its doors and create opportunities for research and continuing education in their respective areas of comparative advantage. As per need of the hour, Higher Education will be merit-based, needs sensitive and strive for intellectual excellence.

References:

1. Research Handbook-Towards Nurturing Culture in Higher Education, Published by UGC, New Delhi.
2. Reinventing Education for an inclusive world, The Lecture was delivered by Prof. Yas Pal at M.G. University Kottayam.
3. Birendra Deka, "HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA: (DEVELOPMENT AND PROBLEMS)", Atlantic Publications.

